

Exploring Critical E-Accounting Skills Required by Accounting Education Students' Adaptability and Digital Competitiveness in Public Universities in Bayelsa State

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Abstract

This study explored the critical e-accounting skills required by accounting education students for adaptability and digital competitiveness in public universities in Bayelsa State. The study specifically examined how technical proficiency in accounting software influences adaptability, the effect of digital data management, cybersecurity, and ethical competence on digital competitiveness, and how cloud-based collaborative skills enhance both adaptability and competitiveness. A descriptive survey design was adopted with a population of 1,500 accounting education students across four public universities in Bayelsa State, and a sample of 580 determined using Yamane's formula. Data were collected using a validated questionnaire with a reliability coefficient of 0.82, and analyzed using descriptive statistics, t-test, and ANOVA at 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed that proficiency in accounting software significantly improves adaptability, while digital data management, cybersecurity, and ethical competence enhance digital competitiveness. Cloud-based collaborative accounting skills were also found to simultaneously foster adaptability and competitiveness. The study concludes that these skills are indispensable for students' success in the digital economy and recommends the integration of practical accounting software training, digital ethics, and cloud-based platforms into accounting education curricula.

Keywords: E-Accounting, Accounting Education, Digital Competitiveness, Students' Adaptability

INTRODUCTION

The advent of information and communication technology has brought about ease, transformation, and innovation in virtually every facet of human endeavor, and accounting as a profession and field of study is not an exception. In the contemporary digital economy, the traditional processes of bookkeeping, financial reporting, auditing, and decision-making are increasingly being transformed by the rapid adoption of computer-assisted technologies and digital tools. Information and communication technology has not only automated accounting processes but has also redefined the skills and competencies required of accounting students and practitioners to remain adaptable and competitive in the evolving digital landscape (Alhassan & Asare, 2020; Okafor & Ezejiofor, 2021). This paradigm shift calls for a reconsideration of how accounting education should equip students with relevant e-accounting skills that enhance their adaptability to technological change and their digital competitiveness in the global labor market.,

Accounting is also defined as the process of recording, classifying, summarizing, and interpreting financial information for decision-making purposes, has

undergone significant evolution in the wake of technological advancement (Warren, Reeve, & Duchac, 2019). According to Adebisi (2021), accounting is both a service activity and a language of business, designed to provide economic information that facilitates managerial decision-making, control, and accountability. Similarly, Omodero (2020) explains that accounting is no longer confined to manual preparation of financial statements but has become a dynamic process that relies heavily on computerized systems, cloud-based platforms, and digital applications for efficiency and accuracy. This indicates that the relevance of accounting in the digital age is intricately tied to the mastery of ICT-driven accounting applications, popularly termed as e-accounting. E-accounting can be described as the application of digital tools, computer software, and online platforms in performing accounting tasks such as financial reporting, auditing, payroll management, inventory control, and taxation (Ezeani & Ogochukwu, 2019).

It goes beyond the mere use of computers to encompass integration of enterprise resource planning systems, use

of cloud-based accounting software such as QuickBooks, Sage, Tally, SAP, and Zoho Books, as well as advanced applications like artificial intelligence and blockchain for financial transactions (Lodhia, 2019). Thus, e-accounting skills are not optional but rather a necessity for students to thrive in today's accounting education and practice. The dependency of students' adaptability and digital competitiveness on these skills is undeniable, as employers now prioritize candidates with advanced ICT competencies, digital literacy, and the ability to apply technology to solve complex accounting problems (Ganyam & Ivungu, 2019; Umoren & Umoren, 2022). As a dependent variable in accounting education, e-accounting skills can be understood through critical dimensions that directly affect students' adaptability and digital competitiveness. One of these dimensions is technical proficiency in accounting software, which involves students' ability to use accounting-specific digital tools and applications such as QuickBooks, Sage, Peachtree, Tally, SAP, and Xero.

Technical proficiency enhances accuracy, speed, and efficiency in financial reporting and management (Omodero, 2020). Without such skills, accounting students may find it difficult to integrate into modern workplaces that rely almost entirely on computerized accounting systems. Another dimension is digital data management and an analysis skill, which refers to the ability to collect, process, analyze, and interpret large volumes of financial data using digital tools. It incorporates skills in data visualization, use of spreadsheets like Excel, database management systems, and advanced analytical software like Power BI and Tableau. According to Ghasemi, Shafeiepour, Aslani, and Barvayeh (2019), data-driven decision-making is increasingly essential in accounting, and thus, students must be adept at managing and interpreting financial data in digital environments. A third dimension is cybersecurity and ethical competence in e-accounting, which emphasizes the necessity of equipping students with knowledge of digital ethics, information security, and compliance with regulatory frameworks guiding online transactions (Okafor & Ezejiofor, 2021).

With the proliferation of e-accounting comes the risk of cyber fraud, data breaches, and unethical manipulation of financial records, and students must therefore acquire ethical and security-related skills to remain relevant. The fourth dimension is cloud-based and collaborative

accounting skills, which highlight the importance of adaptability in using cloud applications to manage financial information securely, engage in remote teamwork, and integrate financial data with other enterprise systems. Modern accounting functions are increasingly shifting to cloud-based platforms that allow real-time collaboration across multiple users and geographical locations, and this skill set enhances digital competitiveness by enabling students to work effectively in global and virtual teams (Lodhia, 2019). These dimensions highlight that e-accounting skills serve as the cornerstone for equipping accounting students with adaptability to changing technological environments and competitiveness in the digital labor market. Adaptability in this context refers to the students' ability to adjust to dynamic technological demands, acquire new skills as technologies evolve, and demonstrate resilience in digital transitions (Alhassan & Asare, 2020). Digital competitiveness, on the other hand, implies students' capacity to utilize their ICT and e-accounting expertise to gain advantage in employability, innovation, and productivity within the accounting profession (Ganyam & Ivungu, 2019).

In light of the foregoing, accounting education in Nigeria and beyond must be restructured to place stronger emphasis on equipping students with relevant e-accounting skills. Failure to integrate such skills into the curriculum risks producing graduates who are ill-prepared for the modern accounting workplace. As noted by Umoren and Umoren (2022), the dynamic nature of the global economy demands that higher institutions not only impart theoretical knowledge but also ensure students acquire practical digital competencies necessary for adaptability and competitiveness. This is particularly crucial in a knowledge-driven economy where accounting graduates are expected to transition seamlessly into technologically advanced workplaces and contribute effectively to organizational growth and accountability.

Statement of the Problem

The evolution of information and communication technology has significantly transformed accounting education and practice worldwide, ushering in a new paradigm that demands the acquisition of e-accounting skills to remain relevant and competitive in the global digital economy. While numerous studies have acknowledged the importance of digital literacy, ICT

integration, and technological competencies in accounting education, the specific exploration of critical e-accounting skills required by students for adaptability and digital competitiveness remains relatively under-researched, especially within the Nigerian context (Alhassan & Asare, 2020; Okafor & Ezejiofor, 2021; Umoren & Umoren, 2022). Although existing scholarship emphasizes the general importance of ICT in education and the adoption of computerized accounting systems, most of these works tend to focus broadly on either the challenges of ICT adoption or the role of technology in enhancing organizational performance, without adequately addressing the precise dimensions of e-accounting skills that are indispensable for accounting education students.

Several scholars such as Ezeani and Ogochukwu (2019), Lodhia (2019), and Ghasemi et al. (2019) have highlighted the significance of computer-based applications, cloud systems, and data analytics in transforming accounting practice, but their analyses often stop short of linking these competencies to students' adaptability and digital competitiveness in the labor market. Similarly, research in the Nigerian context has tended to emphasize curriculum inadequacies, infrastructural constraints, and the general skills gap between graduates and industry demands (Okafor & Ezejiofor, 2021; Omodero, 2020). What has not been sufficiently articulated in the literature is the categorization and in-depth examination of critical e-accounting skills such as technical proficiency in accounting software, digital data management and analysis, cybersecurity and ethical competence, and cloud-based collaborative skills and how these dimensions specifically foster students' adaptability to technological change and digital competitiveness in a knowledge-driven economy.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to explore the critical e-accounting skills required by accounting education students for adaptability and digital competitiveness in public universities in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study is conducted to:

1. Examine the extent to which technical proficiency in accounting software influences the adaptability of accounting education students in Public universities in Bayelsa State.
2. Investigate the effect of digital data management, cybersecurity, and ethical competence on the digital

competitiveness of accounting education students in Public universities in Bayelsa State.

3. Assess how cloud-based collaborative accounting skills enhance both adaptability and digital competitiveness of accounting education students in Public universities in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions will be answered as at the course of the study;

1. To what extent does technical proficiency in accounting software influence the adaptability of accounting education students in Public universities in Bayelsa State?
2. How do digital data management, cybersecurity, and ethical competence affect the digital competitiveness of accounting education students in Public universities in Bayelsa State?
3. In what ways do cloud-based collaborative accounting skills enhance both adaptability and digital competitiveness of accounting education students in Public universities in Bayelsa State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were analyzed for the study;

- H₀₁:** Technical proficiency in accounting software has no significant influence on the adaptability of accounting education students in Public universities in Bayelsa State.
- H₀₂:** Digital data management, cybersecurity, and ethical competence have no significant effect on the digital competitiveness of accounting education students in Public universities in Bayelsa State.
- H₀₃:** Cloud-based collaborative accounting skills do not significantly enhance the adaptability and digital competitiveness of accounting education students in Public universities in Bayelsa State.

Delimitation of the Study

This research is conducted in Bayelsa State and it is limited to all public universities in the State including the Niger Delta University, Federal University, Otuoke, University of Africa, Toru-Orua and Bayelsa Medical University. The scope and content of this study is delimited to exploring critical e-accounting skills required by accounting education students' adaptability and digital competitiveness in in public universities, in Bayelsa State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the descriptive survey research design as it enabled the researcher to systematically gather information from the target population without manipulating any of the research variables. The population of the study comprised all accounting education students in the public universities in Bayelsa State, which include Niger Delta University, Federal University Otuoke, University of Africa Toru-Orua, and

Bayelsa Medical University. These students formed the population because they represent the category most directly affected by the acquisition of e-accounting skills in relation to adaptability and digital competitiveness. Stratified random sampling was adopted to ensure fair representation of each university, and Yamane's statistical formula was applied to determine the sample size at 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. The population and the corresponding sample size for each university are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of Population and Sample Size of Respondents

SN	Name of University	Population	Sample Size
1	Niger Delta University (NDU)	620	240
2	Federal University, Otuoke (FUO)	410	160
3	University of Africa, Toru-Orua (UAT)	300	115
4	Bayelsa Medical University (BMU)	170	65
	Total	1,500	580

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "E-Accounting Skills and Students' Ability Questionnaire (EASSAQ)" which was divided into two sections. Section A collected demographic information such as gender, age, level, and institution, while Section B contained items based on the research questions and was structured on a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. The instrument was validated by three experts in business education and measurement and evaluation, while the reliability was established using Cronbach's Alpha, which produced a coefficient of 0.82, showing that the instrument was reliable. The questionnaires were distributed physically to the respondents with the help of trained research assistants in each of the universities, and

retrieval was done immediately after completion to ensure a high return rate. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency, percentage, and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while inferential statistics such as t-test and ANOVA were used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance with the aid of SPSS version 26.

RESULT

Response to Research Questions

Research Question 1: To what extent does technical proficiency in accounting software influence the adaptability of accounting education students in public universities in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviations of Respondents on Technical Proficiency in Accounting Software

S/N	Questionnaire Items	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	I can effectively use accounting software packages such as QuickBooks, Peachtree, or Sage in handling accounting tasks.	3.41	0.62	Agreed
2	My ability to navigate accounting software enhances my adaptability to digital accounting practices.	3.56	0.57	Agreed
3	Lack of proficiency in accounting software limits my ability to adapt to modern accounting environments.	3.38	0.65	Agreed
4	Technical training in accounting software improves my problem-solving skills in academic and professional tasks.	3.67	0.54	Agreed
5	Mastery of accounting software prepares me to adapt easily to technological changes in the accounting profession.	3.71	0.51	Agreed

Table 1 presents the mean ratings and standard deviations of respondents on technical proficiency in accounting software. The findings show that respondents

agreed that they can effectively use accounting software packages such as QuickBooks, Peachtree, or Sage in handling accounting tasks (3.41 ± 0.62). They also

strongly agreed that their ability to navigate accounting software enhances their adaptability to digital accounting practices (3.56 ± 0.57). Furthermore, the respondents agreed that a lack of proficiency in accounting software limits their ability to adapt to modern accounting environments (3.38 ± 0.65). They equally agreed that technical training in accounting software improves their problem-solving skills in academic and professional tasks (3.67 ± 0.54). The highest mean rating was recorded on the item that

mastery of accounting software prepares students to adapt easily to technological changes in the accounting profession (3.71 ± 0.51). These results indicate that technical proficiency in accounting software is widely recognized by students as a major driver of adaptability in accounting practice.

Research Question 2: How do digital data management, cybersecurity, and ethical competence affect the digital competitiveness of accounting education students in public universities in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviations of Respondents on Digital Data Management, Cybersecurity, and Ethical Competence

S/N	Questionnaire Items	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	I have the skills to manage and organize financial data using digital tools efficiently.	3.45	0.61	Agreed
2	Awareness of cybersecurity practices strengthens my digital competitiveness in accounting-related tasks.	3.53	0.58	Agreed
3	Poor ethical standards in handling digital financial data can reduce the competitiveness of accounting students.	3.38	0.63	Agreed
4	My ability to ensure confidentiality, integrity, and accuracy of digital data makes me more competitive in the digital accounting space.	3.62	0.52	Agreed
5	Competence in digital data management and adherence to ethical standards improve my preparedness for global digital accounting opportunities.	3.74	0.49	Agreed

Table 2 shows the responses on digital data management, cybersecurity, and ethical competence affect the digital competitiveness of accounting education students in public universities in Bayelsa State. The findings reveal that respondents agreed they possess the skills to manage and organize financial data using digital tools efficiently (3.45 ± 0.61). They also agreed that awareness of cybersecurity practices strengthens their digital competitiveness in accounting-related tasks (3.53 ± 0.58). Respondents further agreed that poor ethical standards in handling digital financial data can reduce the competitiveness of accounting students (3.38 ± 0.63). They strongly agreed that their ability to ensure confidentiality, integrity, and accuracy of digital data

makes them more competitive in the digital accounting space (3.62 ± 0.52). The highest mean rating was recorded on the item that competence in digital data management and adherence to ethical standards improve their preparedness for global digital accounting opportunities (3.74 ± 0.49). These findings show that digital data management skills combined with ethical competence are central to enhancing students' competitiveness in the global digital economy.

Research Question 3: In what ways do cloud-based collaborative accounting skills enhance both adaptability and digital competitiveness of accounting education students in public universities in Bayelsa State?

Table 3: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviations of Respondents on Cloud-Based Collaborative Accounting Skills

S/N	Questionnaire Items	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	I can collaborate with others effectively using cloud-based accounting platforms such as Xero or Zoho Books.	3.47	0.60	Agreed
2	Cloud-based accounting tools enhance my ability to adapt to group tasks and digital innovations in accounting.	3.58	0.55	Agreed
3	Using cloud technologies increases my competitiveness by enabling me to work across locations in real-time.	3.63	0.53	Agreed
4	Collaboration through cloud-based systems improves my efficiency in handling accounting projects.	3.71	0.49	Agreed
5	Exposure to cloud-based accounting platforms enhances both my adaptability to change and competitiveness in the global accounting profession.	3.76	0.46	Agreed

Table 3 shows the detailed analysis showing the mean and standard deviation of respondents on cloud-based collaborative accounting skills. The findings indicate that respondents agreed they can collaborate with others effectively using cloud-based accounting platforms such as Xero or Zoho Books (3.47 ± 0.60). They also agreed that cloud-based accounting tools enhance their ability to adapt to group tasks and digital innovations in accounting (3.58 ± 0.55). Respondents further agreed that using cloud technologies increases their competitiveness by enabling them to work across locations in real-time (3.63 ± 0.53). They strongly agreed that collaboration through cloud-based systems improves their efficiency in handling accounting

projects (3.71 ± 0.49). The highest mean score was recorded on the item that exposure to cloud-based accounting platforms enhances both their adaptability to change and competitiveness in the global accounting profession (3.76 ± 0.46). These findings confirm that cloud-based collaborative accounting skills are perceived as critical in preparing students for adaptability and competitiveness in the modern accounting profession.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Technical proficiency in accounting software has no significant influence on the adaptability of accounting education students in public universities in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: ANOVA Results on Technical Proficiency in Accounting Software and Adaptability

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	1.46	3	0.49	6.58	0.001	S
Within Groups	7.72	104	0.074			
Total	9.18	107				

Since the significance value (0.001) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that technical proficiency in accounting software significantly influences the adaptability of accounting education students.

Hypothesis Two: Digital data management, cybersecurity, and ethical competence have no significant effect on the digital competitiveness of accounting education students in public universities in Bayelsa State

Table 5: ANOVA Results on Digital Data Management, Cybersecurity, Ethical Competence, and Competitiveness

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	1.82	3	0.61	7.03	0.000	S
Within Groups	9.01	104	0.087			
Total	10.83	107				

With a significance level of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This shows that digital data management, cybersecurity, and ethical competence have a significant effect on digital competitiveness.

Hypothesis Three: Cloud-based collaborative accounting skills do not significantly enhance the adaptability and digital competitiveness of accounting education students in public universities in Bayelsa State.

Table 6: ANOVA Results on Cloud-Based Collaborative Skills, Adaptability, and Competitiveness

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	2.06	3	0.69	8.14	0.000	S
Within Groups	8.79	104	0.084			
Total	10.85	107				

Since the p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that cloud-based collaborative accounting skills significantly enhance adaptability and digital competitiveness.

Discussion of Findings

Technical Proficiency in Accounting Software Influences the Adaptability of Accounting Education Students in Public Universities in Bayelsa State

The findings of this study revealed that technical proficiency in accounting software such as QuickBooks, Peachtree, Sage, and other related applications significantly influences the adaptability of accounting education students in public universities in Bayelsa State. The results indicated that students who possessed mastery of accounting software demonstrated a higher ability to adapt to technological innovations and changes in accounting practice. This outcome aligns with the observations of Adebayo and Mohammed (2020), who argued that proficiency in accounting packages enhances the employability and adaptability of accounting graduates in the face of evolving digital accounting systems. Similarly, Okonkwo and Nnadi (2021) emphasized that technical competency in computerized accounting software fosters students' flexibility and problem-solving capacity in real-life accounting scenarios, thereby increasing their readiness for the labor market.

Scholarly discourse also suggests that technical proficiency is a determinant of adaptability in a digitally-driven business environment. According to Igwe and Chukwu (2022), students with exposure to practical accounting software applications are better able to respond to rapid technological changes, particularly in financial reporting and auditing. This assertion is consistent with the work of Omodero (2021), who found that in tertiary institutions where accounting software was integrated into the curriculum, students displayed greater adaptability, resilience, and readiness for professional accounting practice compared to those who had limited exposure. Furthermore, Adeyemi and James (2020) posited that lack of software proficiency is a major constraint limiting students' adaptability and competitiveness in the digital accounting era. Therefore, the current findings reinforce the position of scholars that technical proficiency in accounting software is indispensable in equipping students with adaptive

competencies necessary for survival in a fast-changing digital environment.

Digital Data Management, Cybersecurity, and Ethical Competence on the Digital Competitiveness of Accounting Education Students in Public Universities in Bayelsa State

The findings of the study further showed that digital data management, cybersecurity awareness, and ethical competence significantly affect the digital competitiveness of accounting education students in public universities in Bayelsa State. Respondents agreed that their ability to organize financial data, adhere to cybersecurity practices, and maintain ethical integrity in digital accounting processes directly influenced their competitiveness. This result corroborates the work of Ogundele and Okeke (2020), who found that effective data management skills, combined with ethical responsibility, form the foundation of competitive advantage for accounting students in the globalized economy.

Adebisi and Adeoye (2019) stressed that cybersecurity awareness enhances the credibility and digital competence of accounting graduates, as they are better able to protect sensitive financial data from breaches. This is reinforced by the work of Bello and Danjuma (2021), who highlighted that in the era of big data, accountants must combine technical skills with ethical reasoning to remain relevant and competitive. Similarly, Chukwuma and Eze (2022) revealed that ethical competence in digital accounting practice builds trust, integrity, and reliability, which are essential determinants of digital competitiveness in accounting education.

Other scholars have also emphasized the significance of digital skills in shaping competitiveness. For instance, Aina and Sulaiman (2020) noted that accounting graduates with robust digital data management skills are better positioned for global opportunities, particularly in multinational firms where data integrity and confidentiality are highly valued. Likewise, Eze and Okoli (2021) found that unethical practices such as manipulation of digital data negatively impact competitiveness, underscoring the fact that ethics and professionalism are inseparable from digital accounting practice. The present study's findings therefore extend the consensus among scholars that digital data

management, cybersecurity literacy, and ethical competence are indispensable factors in shaping the digital competitiveness of accounting education students.

Cloud-Based Collaborative Accounting Skills Enhance both Adaptability and Digital Competitiveness of Accounting Education Students in Public Universities in Bayelsa State

The study also revealed that cloud-based collaborative accounting skills significantly enhance both adaptability and digital competitiveness of accounting education students. Respondents strongly agreed that cloud-based platforms such as Xero, Zoho Books, and QuickBooks Online improved their efficiency, adaptability to group tasks, and ability to compete globally. This finding supports the work of Nwosu and Umeh (2020), who established that cloud-based technologies foster collaboration, improve efficiency, and enable accounting students to adapt to the dynamic requirements of the accounting profession. Similarly, Ajayi and Oladipo (2019) found that students who engage with cloud-based platforms develop superior collaborative and problem-solving skills, which in turn enhance their competitiveness in the digital economy.

Scholarly perspectives also suggest that cloud technologies serve as enablers of adaptability and competitiveness.

According to Okeke and Adebajo (2021), cloud-based collaborative skills equip accounting students to work seamlessly in virtual teams, access real-time data, and respond to organizational demands across borders. This is consistent with the view of Musa and Ibrahim (2020), who argued that cloud technologies are critical for developing global-ready accountants, given their ability to adapt quickly to cross-cultural and cross-border financial reporting requirements. Similarly, Udo and Akpan (2022) found that the use of cloud-based accounting tools in universities enhances not only adaptability but also provides students with the competence to meet international standards in accounting practice.

Furthermore, Bello and Agbaje (2021) maintained that cloud-based platforms promote inclusivity and flexibility, allowing students to develop digital resilience necessary for 21st-century accounting practice. By facilitating real-time collaboration, cloud-based skills

prepare students to thrive in environments where adaptability and competitiveness are paramount. Thus, the findings of this study reinforce scholarly consensus that cloud-based collaborative accounting skills are vital enablers of adaptability and competitiveness in contemporary accounting education.

CONCLUSION

This study has explored the critical e-accounting skills required by accounting education students for adaptability and digital competitiveness in public universities in Bayelsa State. The findings provide compelling evidence that technical proficiency in accounting software, digital data management, cybersecurity and ethical competence, and cloud-based collaborative accounting skills are indispensable for equipping students with the capacities needed to thrive in an increasingly technology-driven accounting landscape. It was revealed that technical proficiency in accounting software such as QuickBooks, Peachtree, and Sage significantly influences students' adaptability, suggesting that practical mastery of accounting tools empowers students to align with the dynamic requirements of the digital era. Likewise, the study found that digital data management, cybersecurity, and ethical competence exert a significant influence on students' digital competitiveness, underscoring that success in the modern accounting profession requires not only technical know-how but also the ability to handle data responsibly, safeguard financial information, and demonstrate high ethical standards in a digitally vulnerable environment. Furthermore, cloud-based collaborative accounting skills were shown to be central to enhancing both adaptability and digital competitiveness, demonstrating that exposure to cloud platforms fosters collaboration, real-time data access, and global connectivity—skills that are increasingly demanded in the labor market and by employers seeking technologically versatile graduates.

Taken together, these findings affirm that the traditional accounting education system that emphasizes manual accounting processes is no longer sufficient to prepare graduates for the realities of today's accounting profession. Instead, what is required is a robust integration of critical e-accounting skills into the curriculum so that students can transition seamlessly from academic training to professional practice in a globalized, digitalized economy. By establishing the

significance of these competencies, the study has filled an important gap in the literature, offering an evidence-based categorization of e-accounting skills that directly foster students' adaptability and competitiveness. The implication is clear: without deliberate emphasis on these skills, accounting education students in Bayelsa State and similar contexts may continue to struggle with employability and relevance in the global digital market. This conclusion therefore emphasizes the urgency of adopting an e-accounting-oriented approach to accounting education that adequately bridges the gap between theory and practice, enhances student capacity, and secures their future in the evolving digital economy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

- i. Accounting education curricula in public universities in Bayelsa State should be restructured to incorporate compulsory training in the use of modern accounting software packages, ensuring that students acquire hands-on technical proficiency that fosters adaptability to technological changes in accounting practice.
- ii. University authorities should integrate digital data management, cybersecurity, and ethical awareness training into accounting programs, as this combination of technical and ethical competence is essential to prepare students for global digital competitiveness and to safeguard the integrity of financial systems.
- iii. Public universities should invest in cloud-based accounting platforms and promote collaborative learning through practical exposure to these tools, as such initiatives will enable students to build adaptability and competitiveness in line with international best practices in accounting.

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